

1 **European Modes of Circulation Variability**

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22

23 **Abstract**

24 The key challenge of dynamic climatology has always been to describe and understand the
25 large-scale variability in atmospheric circulation with the purpose of interpreting weather
26 extremes and climate variability. In Europe, the classical concept of Euro–Atlantic weather
27 regimes has been commonly adopted, with an emphasis placed primarily on Western Europe
28 and its atmospheric connection to the North Atlantic Oscillation. However, these regimes often
29 fail to explain a relatively large proportion of the variability in basic meteorological variables
30 and their spatial patterns across more continental parts of Europe, particularly with respect to
31 precipitation and connected variables (such as soil moisture). Here, we address this research
32 gap by implementing a novel, machine-learning-based approach to define European Modes of
33 circulation variability (EMoCs). In a Europe-centric domain (40°W–60°E, 30°–80°N), we
34 employed 500-hPa geopotential height anomalies from European Centre of Medium-Range
35 Weather Forecasts Reanalysis v.5 (ERA5) data for the 1981–2023 period to train 300 individual
36 self-organizing map (SOM) neural networks and combined them into a single SOM model. The
37 resulting dataset was then clustered by Wards’ clustering method, which facilitated the
38 identification of four main EMoCs: Atlantic blocking (ABL), Continental blocking (CBL),
39 Southern zonal track (SZT) and Northern zonal track (NZT). Using best-matching unit (BMU)
40 calculations, these four EMoCs were assigned to individual days, which allowed the
41 classification of days outside the SOM training period and the extension of the series to the
42 longer 1940–2023 period. Moreover, this approach could enable the use of the EMoC
43 classification for weather forecasts. Each EMoC represents highly distinct spatial patterns of

44 weather conditions across Europe. In particular, SZT and NZT lead to very dry/wet patterns
45 over Central and Western Europe, even though both modes represent enhanced zonal flow
46 patterns over the North Atlantic. The four main EMOCs could serve as useful tools for dynamic
47 climatology, future climate projections and season-to-season weather forecasts.

48

49 **Keywords:** atmospheric circulation, European modes of circulation variability, self-
50 organizing maps, temperature, precipitation, soil moisture

51

52 **1 Introduction**

53 Understanding the large-scale variability in atmospheric circulation over Europe has always
54 remained a key challenge of dynamic climatology, particularly with the purpose of interpreting
55 weather extremes and climate trends across the continent (Sippel et al. 2020; Vihma et al. 2020).
56 At the regional scale, detailed classifications of atmospheric circulation are typically applied
57 across Europe (Bissolli and Dittmann 2001; Huth et al., 2008; Mika et al. 2021), thereby usually
58 defining double-digit numbers of circulation types. In the past, these classifications were
59 prepared using methods based on subjective evaluation of sea-level pressure fields, such as the
60 classification of Grosswetterlagen, which was developed for Central Europe (Hess and
61 Brezowsky 1952; Gerstengarbe and Werner 1993), or subjective classification for individual
62 European countries (Brádka 1972; Osuchowska-Klein 1978), which were later replaced by
63 objective classifications based on a large variety of algorithmic methods (James 2007; Hansen
64 and Belušić 2021; Řehoř et al. 2021).

65 However, moving to the continental scale, the aim is to define a limited number of
66 dominant and spatially coherent patterns that explain most of the variability in the mid-
67 tropospheric pressure field while avoiding overfitting (Michelangeli et al. 1995; Hannachi et al.
68 2017). This variability is often characterized by teleconnection indices such as the North
69 Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), East Atlantic (EA), East Atlantic/Western Russia (EA/WRP) or
70 Scandinavian (SCA) patterns (Hurrell 2001, 2003; Krichak and Alpert 2005; Comas-Bru and
71 Mcdermott 2014; Liu et al. 2014), which describe dominant modes of tropospheric pressure
72 field anomalies (Barnston and Livezey 1987). The aforementioned indices provide easily
73 interpretable diagnostics of circulation patterns and enable their long-term analysis; however,
74 the multidimensional structure of circulation is reduced to a few measures in these indices
75 (Woollings et al. 2010).

76 To capture more spatially complex and persistent features of atmospheric circulation,
77 alternative approaches have been developed to describe circulation variability on the basis of a
78 small set of low-dimensional modes (Vautard 1990; Falkena et al. 2020; Hochman et al. 2021).
79 The determination of these modes (often referred to as Euro–Atlantic weather regimes)
80 typically relies on the application of empirical orthogonal functions (EOFs) to fields of the 500-
81 hPa geopotential height (alternatively the 700-hPa geopotential height) to reduce the
82 dimensionality of the data into a few principal components (Slonosky et al. 2000; Dawson et
83 al. 2012). These approaches are often combined with the k-means clustering method (Madonna
84 et al. 2017; Fabiano et al. 2021), although both methods have also been applied separately (Huth
85 et al. 2008; Cattiaux et al. 2010). Among alternative clustering techniques coupled with EOFs
86 for clustering, self-organizing maps (SOMs) have been employed by Vihma et al. (2020),
87 whereas circulation classifications (in general) performed solely by SOMs have been applied
88 many times (Cassano et al. 2006; Sheridan and Lee 2011; Ambrožová et al. 2020). However,
89 the option to use SOMs instead of EOFs for initial dimensionality reduction in the two-stage
90 clustering process has not been investigated fully, although SOMs are regularly applied in other
91 scientific fields, such as economics or neuroscience (Canetta et al. 2005; Sheng-Chai and Chih-

92 Chieh 2008), and they are often combined with hierarchical clustering methods (Yorek et al.
93 2016).

94 Although the most typical number of traditional Euro–Atlantic weather regimes, defined
95 in the recent literature, is four (Fabiano et al. 2020; Rantanen et al. 2023), some researchers
96 have opted for more detailed classifications (Beerli and Grams 2019; Falkena et al. 2020). In
97 terms of the variability in basic meteorological variables explained by traditional regimes, the
98 temperature is generally well reflected across the entire continent (Rantanen et al. 2023).
99 Precipitation characteristics are well connected to regimes mostly over Atlantic and Western
100 Europe, whereas such relationships fail toward more continental parts of Europe (Madonna et
101 al. 2021). This failure is likely related to the fact that traditional regimes are closely connected
102 to the NAO, which is notably correlated with precipitation in more northern and southern
103 European areas but not in regions at approximately 50° N (Steirou et al. 2017).

104 The Atlantic-centric approach of traditional Euro–Atlantic weather regimes has been
105 demonstrated by the selected domains, which typically range from 80°–90° W but are restricted
106 to only 30°–40° E (Ferranti et al. 2015; Fabiano et al. 2020; Rantanen et al. 2023), which places
107 most of the domain around the center of the North Atlantic to explain the majority of its
108 circulation variability. Therefore, there is a research gap in terms of the identification of more
109 European landmass-centric principal modes of circulation variability that can explain larger
110 proportions of precipitation variance (perhaps soil moisture anomalies) and their spatial patterns
111 across Europe (including Central and Eastern Europe). The main aims of this paper were as
112 follows: (i) to develop a robust classification system centered over the European landmass; (ii)
113 to assess whether such an approach could facilitate the characterization of particular patterns of
114 temperature, precipitation, sea surface temperature (SST) and soil moisture anomalies; and (iii)
115 to consider whether such an approach could be useful for the eventual improvement in extreme
116 hydrometeorological forecasts (including droughts or floods) across Europe.

117

118 **2 Data and methods**

119 **2.1 Data**

120 Individual European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) were defined primarily on the
121 basis of 500-hPa geopotential height fields from European Centre of Medium-Range Weather
122 Forecasts Reanalysis v.5 (ERA5) atmospheric reanalysis data (Hersbach et al. 2020).
123 Additionally, the following ERA5 variables were used: (i) 200- and 850-hPa geopotential
124 heights, (ii) the air temperature at 2 m above ground, (iii) precipitation totals and (iv) the SST
125 over the 1940–2023 period. Moreover, mean daily temperatures and daily precipitation totals
126 were sourced from the gridded E-OBS dataset (Cornes et al., 2018) to include data based on in
127 situ observations. The available water deficit (AWD) was derived from global simulations of
128 the SoilClim model (Hlavinka et al. 2011; Řehoř et al. 2024); the AWD represents the soil
129 moisture anomaly (in mm) and was calculated separately for each grid (0.1° resolution) and day
130 of the year within a 21-day smoothing window.

131

132 **2.2 Methods**

133 We adopted a Europe-centric domain (40° W–60° E, 30°–80° N), extending partially into the
134 North Atlantic and centered on the northwestern edge of Central Europe (10° E, 55° N). In this
135 domain, anomalies of 500-hPa geopotential height (hereafter referred to as Z500A) were
136 calculated on a daily basis by subtracting the seasonal cycle from the original ERA5 fields using
137 the 1981–2023 reference period. The seasonal cycle was calculated for each day of the year
138 with a 21-day running window to avoid higher frequency fluctuations due to internal variability.
139 Z500A was then calculated for the entire 1940–2023 period and rescaled to a 1° resolution
140 (from the original 0.25° resolution) through the use of bilinear interpolation to reduce the degree

141 of computational complexity. This interpolation does not affect the results, mainly because we
 142 are interested in large-scale patterns.

143 To define the EMOCs, we employed a two-stage clustering approach, thereby using an
 144 SOM neural network (Kohonen 1982) and Ward’s clustering method (Ward 1963). To reduce
 145 the dimensionality of the data at the first stage, we trained 300 individual SOMs on the basis of
 146 daily Z500A fields over the 1981–2023 reference period. The SOM topology was set to 25×25
 147 nodes, and we employed 248 training cycles (epochs), with both parameters based on the
 148 dimensionality of the input dataset (Kohonen 1990; Chi and Yang 2008). The training process
 149 relied on an adaptive neighborhood function and a decreasing learning rate to ensure the gradual
 150 adjustment of the nodes to the input data (Kiang 2001). All 300 trained SOMs were
 151 subsequently combined into a single SOM model by averaging weights at the corresponding
 152 nodes.

153 At the second stage, the nodes of the final SOM model were clustered using a
 154 hierarchical agglomerative approach, specifically Ward’s method (Everitt et al. 2001), which
 155 merges clusters that cause the smallest increase in the error sum of squares and clusters were
 156 extracted for clustering levels of 2–30. Moreover, we conducted a sensitivity analysis by
 157 implementing the entire two-stage process using only single SOMs or a combined model based
 158 on a substantially smaller number of SOMs and then compared the similarity within clusters
 159 and between clusters by the silhouette method (Rousseeuw 1987). As shown in Fig. S1, the
 160 degree of cluster consistency generally increased with increasing number of SOMs used for the
 161 clustered model across all clustering levels, whereas the variability between different cluster
 162 delimitations decreased. Therefore, using a final SOM model based on all 300 SOMs was
 163 considered the most robust and suitable approach.

164 To connect the Ward-derived clusters to the original Z500A dataset (i.e., to assign one
 165 cluster to each day), a best-matching unit (BMU) (Kaya et al. 2017; Miljković 2017) was
 166 calculated for each day, which represents the node with the highest similarity (smallest
 167 Euclidean distance) to the input Z500A vector for that day. The cluster belonging to a given
 168 BMU is subsequently inherited by the given day. Because the BMU can also be calculated for
 169 Z500A data outside the 1981–2023 reference period, the time series was extended to the entire
 170 1940–2023 period, while using the SOM model trained on the basis of the 1981–2023 reference
 171 period and included pre-1980 data. A scheme of the entire process is shown in Fig. 1.

172

173
 174 **Fig. 1** Basic scheme of the EMOc classification process

175

176 To select the optimal clustering level, the number of final EMoCs using silhouette
177 analysis (Fig. S1) was considered together with the numbers used in previous research on large-
178 scale circulation variability in Europe (Fabiano et al. 2020; Rantanen et al. 2023). Both factors
179 indicated the selection of four clusters, i.e., four EMoCs, which we present herein as our
180 finalized classification output.

181 With respect to the study periods, the decision to start most analyses in 1981 was based
182 on the higher spatiotemporal consistency of ERA5 data since the introduction of satellite data
183 (Soci et al. 2024). To consider pre-1981 data, we analyzed data from 1940–1957 and 1958–
184 1980 separately, thereby considering the greater radiosonde data availability since 1958. The
185 analysis results are presented for individual seasons (winter, i.e., December, January and
186 February (DJF); spring, i.e., March, April and May (MAM); summer, i.e., June, July and August
187 (JJA); and autumn, i.e., September, October and November (SON)), the winter half-year
188 (WHY, October–March) and the summer half-year (SHY, April–September).

189 Linear trends in EMoCs frequencies were calculated using the nonparametric Theil–Sen
190 regression method (Theil 1992; Sen 2012), which is robust to outliers. The statistical
191 significance of trends was evaluated using the nonparametric Mann–Kendall test (Mann 1945;
192 Kendall 1975) at $p < 0.05$.

193

194 **3 Results**

195 **3.1 European modes of circulation variability**

196 On the basis of the mean 500-hPa geopotential heights and their anomalies (Z500A) with
197 respect to the 1981–2023 reference period during individual EMoCs and considering the
198 identified spatial features of Z500A, the following four final EMoCs were defined (Fig. 2):
199

199

- 200 (i) Atlantic blocking (ABL);
- 201 (ii) Continental blocking (CBL);
- 202 (iii) Southern zonal track (SZT); and
- 203 (iv) Northern zonal track (NZT).

204

205 ABL is particularly characterized by a positive Z500A southward of Iceland, followed by a
206 negative Z500A in northeastern Europe. In the case of CBL, a positive Z500A is centered over
207 northern Scandinavia, while there is only a slight negative Z500A at approximately 45° N in
208 Atlantic and Western Europe. Both ABL and CBL can be characterized by blocking patterns
209 with lower latitudinal gradients of 500-hPa geopotential heights. In contrast, SZT and NZT
210 represent patterns with stronger latitudinal gradients of 500-hPa geopotential heights. However,
211 their patterns around Central and Northwestern Europe significantly differ. SZT is
212 characterized by a strong negative Z500A centered on Scotland, caused by a trough of a lower
213 500-hPa geopotential height in the area of the British Isles, which is frequently connected with
214 the track of Atlantic cyclones toward Central Europe or southern Scandinavia. In contrast, NZT
215 is represented by strong positive Z500A values over Western and Central Europe and strong
216 negative Z500A values around Iceland and toward Greenland, indicating cyclogenesis in the
217 area, but the cyclone track is more likely to shift toward northern Scandinavia or the Barents
218 Sea.

219

220
 221 **Fig. 2** Mean 500-hPa geopotential heights and their anomalies (with respect to the 1981–2023
 222 reference period; Z500A) for the four basic European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs)
 223 during the 1981–2023 period
 224

225 The consistency of the EMoC patterns in the pressure field anomalies throughout the
 226 troposphere is shown in Fig. S2 at the 200- and 850-hPa pressure levels (representing the lower
 227 and upper troposphere, respectively). There is only a slight shift in the identified anomalies
 228 toward the southeast at the 850-hPa level compared with the 200-hPa level.
 229

230 **3.2 Temperature, precipitation and soil moisture under the European modes of** 231 **circulation variability**

232 With respect to temperature anomaly patterns, ABL is the coldest mode in most of Europe,
 233 particularly in the northeast. In contrast, Nzt is the warmest mode in the northwestern half of
 234 Europe, whereas SZT is warmer toward the southeast (Fig. 3). Compared with ERA5-based
 235 anomalies, E-OBS-based anomalies highlight the orographic effect of mountain ranges
 236 (particularly of the Alps), but the differences between the datasets are not very large. In terms
 237 of half-year shifts in temperature patterns, Fig. S3 reveals that the level of seasonality is highest
 238 in the case of CBL, which is colder during the WHY for most of Europe (except for the
 239 southwestern regions), whereas it results in higher temperatures in northern Europe and
 240 temperatures around the mean for the rest of Europe during the SHY. The half-year changes
 241 under the remaining EMoCs are smaller; SZT is colder during the SHY for Western Europe
 242 and warmer during the WHY (except for the British Isles). CBL exhibits temperatures around
 243 the mean across Western Europe during the SHY, with colder conditions during the WHY. The
 244 maximum positive temperature anomalies under the Nzt mode shift from Southwestern
 245 Europe during the SHY to the north during the WHY, but in general, the areas of positive and
 246 negative anomalies remain almost identical.

247
 248 **Fig. 3** Mean temperature anomalies during individual European modes of circulation variability
 249 (EMoCs) based on ERA5 (a) and E-OBS data (b) for 1981–2023
 250

251 With respect to precipitation anomalies (Fig. 4), distinct patterns emerged particularly
 252 for SZT and NZT, with almost exactly opposite behavior. SZT encompassed positive
 253 precipitation anomalies in areas from Western to Central Europe and in Scandinavia, except for

254 the western Norwegian Atlantic coast, where the mean precipitation was below the mean, while
255 the Mediterranean was also drier. In contrast, during NZT, precipitation remained notably
256 below the mean over Central and Western (and partially Eastern) Europe. In Scandinavia, there
257 was a strong gradient with reduced precipitation on the eastern side of the Scandinavian
258 Mountains, while the precipitation on the western side was significantly above the mean. The
259 northwestern Mediterranean remained drier, but the mean precipitation was above the mean in
260 the southern and western parts of the Mediterranean and northern Africa. Between ABL and
261 CBL, the latter was characterized by drier conditions in the northeastern half of Europe,
262 particularly in northwestern Scandinavia, while slightly wetter conditions occurred in the
263 southwestern half of Europe. ABL caused drier conditions around the British Isles and most of
264 Scandinavia and slightly wetter conditions in Eastern Europe and the northern Mediterranean.
265 The half-year changes in precipitation patterns (Fig. S4) were much smaller than those in
266 temperature patterns. However, the patterns were less distinct during the SHY than during the
267 WHY, which is likely related to the higher proportions of convective precipitation during SHY.
268 The greatest differences occurred in the Mediterranean, with NZT being wetter only in its
269 southern part during the WHY, but it revealed strong positive precipitation anomalies during
270 the SHY across most of the area. CBL encompassed slightly wetter conditions during the WHY
271 in the Mediterranean and slightly drier conditions during the SHY. This mode also led to lower
272 precipitation in the northern part of Central Europe during the WHY, while precipitation
273 remained around or above the mean during the SHY.
274

275
 276 **Fig. 4** Mean precipitation anomalies during the European modes of circulation variability
 277 (EMoCs) based on ERA5 (a) and E-OBS data (b) for 1981–2023
 278

279 In terms of mean daily changes in soil moisture (Fig. 5a), NZT stands out among the
 280 four EMoCs because it leads to rapid soil drying over Central, Western and most of Eastern
 281 Europe, with the area extending partially to southern Scandinavia and the northwestern

282 Mediterranean. As shown in Fig. S5, such drying occurs particularly during the SHY in Central
283 Europe, but the rate is much slower during the WHY. Moreover, faster drying occurs during
284 NZT in Southwestern Europe. In contrast, SZT leads to an increase in soil moisture over Central
285 and Western Europe and most of Scandinavia. ABL causes drying on the British Isles and in
286 Scandinavia, while soil moisture in Eastern Europe increases. CBL leads to soil moisture
287 increase in Western Europe and a decrease in soil moisture in Northeastern Europe. The effects
288 of all EMOcs on soil moisture are minimized during the WHY in northern Europe and partially
289 in Central Europe, as the variability in soil moisture is lower in these areas because of the low
290 temperatures. With respect to SST changes (Fig. 5b), ABL leads to cooling in the Baltic Sea
291 area, whereas CBL causes warming. SZT is connected with a decrease in the SST in Western
292 European seas and an increase in the SST in the Black Sea. NZT leads to warming of the Bay
293 of Biscay, North Sea and Baltic Sea, whereas cooling occurs in the Eastern Mediterranean and
294 Black Sea.
295

296
 297 **Fig. 5** Mean changes in daily soil moisture (AWD) (a) and sea surface temperature (SST) (b)
 298 during the European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) over the 1981–2023 period
 299

300 **3.3 Fluctuations in European modes of circulation variability**

301 The seasonal frequencies of the four basic EMoCs over the entire 1940–2023 period exhibit
 302 high interannual variability (Fig. S6), which is generally greater in DJF and SON than in MAM

303 and JJA. Over the past two decades, ABL has become less frequent in DJF and SON, whereas
 304 CBL has become more frequent in JJA. However, among the frequency series of all the EMOs
 305 for individual seasons and half-years (Fig. 6), only the decreasing trend in ABL during the
 306 WHY was statistically significant (-2.2 days per 10 years, $p < 0.05$) over the entire 1940–2023
 307 period. The trends in all the other modes during all the seasons were not statistically significant.
 308

309
 310 **Fig. 6** Absolute and relative frequencies of the four basic European modes of circulation
 311 variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-year (WHY) in the
 312 1940–2023 period, with 10-year Gaussian smoothing (dashed)
 313

314 Seasons with unusually high frequencies of individual EMOs were explored, and the
 315 most prominent cases during the four modes over the 1940–2023 period are shown in Fig. 7.
 316 The absolute maximum seasonal relative frequency of one mode was reached during the very
 317 cold DJF season of 1962/1963 (Sippel et al. 2024), with 81.1% of days (73 days) with the ABL
 318 mode. In general, cases of high frequencies of ABL occurred during all the seasons except JJA,
 319 with DJF dominating over the 1958–1980 period. In contrast, CBL often reached high relative
 320 frequencies in JJA, particularly during the 1940–1957 and 2001–2023 periods. In the case of
 321 SZT and NZT, the seasons were represented more equally, although SON was represented
 322 slightly more and DJF was represented slightly less.
 323

	ABL		CBL		SZT		NZT	
	Season	Frequency (%)						
1940–1957	MAM 1941	67.4	JJA 1947	51.1	JJA 1946	54.3	MAM 1943	46.7
	DJF 1940/1941	62.2	JJA 1950	51.1	JJA 1954	54.3	SON 1953	39.6
	SON 1945	61.5	DJF 1941/1942	41.1	SON 1950	45.1	MAM 1949	38.0
	MAM 1945	59.8	JJA 1941	39.1	DJF 1950/1951	44.4	DJF 1948/1949	36.7
	SON 1941	56.0	JJA 1943	39.1	SON 1944	44.0	SON 1948	33.0
1958–1980	DJF 1962/1963	81.1	DJF 1968/1969	52.2	JJA 1974	53.3	SON 1978	38.5
	SON 1973	79.1	MAM 1960	48.9	DJF 1973/1974	48.9	JJA 1964	38.0
	DJF 1966/1967	67.8	DJF 1971/1972	44.0	MAM 1977	43.5	JJA 1973	35.9
	DJF 1967/1968	58.2	SON 1960	38.5	MAM 1979	42.4	SON 1971	35.2
	DJF 1963/1964	56.0	JJA 1969	38.0	MAM 1967	41.3	JJA 1959	33.7
1981–2000	DJF 1986/1987	68.9	JJA 1997	40.2	SON 1981	51.6	DJF 1988/1989	52.2
	SON 1993	58.2	JJA 1990	38.0	SON 1987	51.6	MAM 1990	43.5
	MAM 1997	54.3	SON 2000	37.4	JJA 1985	48.9	DJF 1991/1992	38.5
	SON 1988	53.8	MAM 1996	35.9	SON 2000	46.2	SON 1986	37.4
	DJF 1984/1985	53.3	SON 1984	34.1	MAM 1986	44.6	JJA 1996	35.9
2001–2023	DJF 2009/2010	58.9	SON 2016	54.9	JJA 2016	45.7	MAM 2011	54.3
	SON 2002	54.9	JJA 2011	53.3	DJF 2013/2014	44.4	DJF 2014/2015	46.7
	MAM 2008	52.2	JJA 2023	51.1	SON 2012	44.0	JJA 2013	41.3
	SON 2001	51.6	DJF 2011/2012	47.3	MAM 2015	42.4	SON 2011	35.2
	MAM 2017	51.1	JJA 2003	42.4	JJA 2001	41.3	JJA 2022	34.8

Fig. 7 Highest seasonal relative frequencies of the occurrence of individual European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) during the 1940–1957, 1958–1980, 1981–2000 and 2001–2023 periods. The colors correspond to the seasons: DJF–blue; MAM–green; JJA–red; SON–yellow

Moreover, the temperature and precipitation patterns of individual EMoCs before 1981 were explored. The mean temperature anomalies and mean precipitation anomalies over the 1940–1957 and 1958–1980 periods are shown in Figs. S7 and S8, respectively. The differences between these periods mostly corresponded to shifts in the mean values, as the 1981–2023 reference period was employed to calculate temperature and precipitation anomalies for all the periods. Because the 1940–1957 and 1958–1980 periods were colder, the whole scale was shifted downward, but the temperature patterns remained almost identical. In terms of precipitation, the 1940–1957 period was drier in Europe than it was during the subsequent periods. Notably, large differences in precipitation patterns were observed only in the Mediterranean, where greater variability and a greater proportion of convective precipitation may cause less stable patterns for individual EMoCs.

4 Discussion

4.1 EMoCs and traditional Euro–Atlantic weather regimes

The concept of four principal quasistationary circulation patterns in the European/North Atlantic region, established by Vautard (1990) and Michelangeli et al. (1995), is usually referred to as Euro–Atlantic weather regimes. In accordance with more recent papers by Fabiano et al. (2021) and Rantanen et al. (2023), the current definitions of these regimes are NAO+, NAO–, Scandinavian blocking and Atlantic ridge. In this study, we introduced EMoCs as an alternative European landmass-centric classification, which retains the conceptual advantages of the classical Euro–Atlantic regimes while yielding sharper and more spatially coherent precipitation and soil-moisture patterns around Central Europe.

A comparison of the Euro–Atlantic weather regimes with the EMoCs reveals that Scandinavian blocking and Atlantic ridge are close to CBL and ABL, although the Z500A patterns of the EMoCs are shifted eastward. However, the concept of the NAO+ and NAO– regimes differs fundamentally from that of the SZT and NZT modes. The NAO+ and NAO– regimes describe the standard NAO dipole over the North Atlantic, with the centers of pressure anomalies almost at the same location for both regimes, with reversed polarity. In contrast, the

358 difference between NZT and SZT is based on the location of the centers of pressure anomalies.
359 NZT encompasses a negative anomaly center far to the northwest in Iceland/Southeast
360 Greenland, while a positive anomaly is centered on Western Europe. During SZT, the negative
361 anomaly center is shifted southeastward around Scotland. With a degree of caution, it can be
362 said that the NAO+ regime constitutes a mean of the NZT and SZT pressure anomalies, whereas
363 the NAO– is morphologically closer to the ABL mode than to either of the zonal track EMOcs.
364 In physical terms, the separation between the EMOcs SZT and NZT can be interpreted as
365 distinguishing alternative storm track displacements: SZT features a trough centered near the
366 British Isles that favors cyclone pathways into Central Europe, whereas NZT shifts cyclonic
367 activity toward higher latitudes, thereby suppressing moisture delivery to Central Europe and
368 promoting drying.

369 This difference explains why the EMOcs can be used to distinguish between very dry
370 and wet circulation patterns in Central and Western Europe (Fig. 4), whereas the NAO-based
371 regimes cannot facilitate the same. As demonstrated by Hurrell (2003), the NAO correlates well
372 with precipitation and the water balance in northern and southern Europe but not in a belt at
373 approximately 50° N. Therefore, NAO-based weather regimes (or other circulation indices)
374 cannot explain precipitation and soil moisture changes in this area (Brázdil et al. 2009). Even
375 if the summer North Atlantic Oscillation (SNAO) is chosen for the SHY, the issue does not
376 improve significantly, as there is still a transect through Central Europe where the SNAO is not
377 correlated with precipitation (Folland et al. 2009, 2024).

378

379 **4.2 Dynamic mechanisms**

380 The drying patterns associated with NZT can also be compared with the results of Sousa et al.
381 (2018), who reported that ridges of high pressure located over Central and Western Europe
382 usually yield larger temperature anomalies because they cause significant disruption of the
383 Atlantic jet stream. Within this context, NZT can be interpreted as a mode associated with a
384 poleward-displaced jet/storm track configuration, suggesting reduced moisture transport into
385 Central and Western Europe and an increased likelihood of persistent anticyclonic conditions
386 and heat extremes (Bischof et al. 2023). As revealed in the presented composites, NZT
387 simultaneously exhibits positive temperature anomalies, negative precipitation anomalies, and
388 rapid AWD decreases over large parts of Europe, thereby highlighting a direct pathway from
389 large-scale dynamics to land-surface drying. Such an interpretation is consistent with previous
390 studies revealing that the variability in the jet stream is complex and cannot be adequately
391 described by a single index, since even the combined NAO and EA patterns cannot fully capture
392 changes in latitude and flow structure (Madonna et al. 2017; Deng et al. 2022).

393 Our temporal analysis results revealed a statistically significant decrease in the
394 frequency of the ABL mode during the WHY from 1940–2023. This decrease may be linked to
395 the varying state of the North Atlantic polar jet stream and phenomena such as Arctic
396 amplification (Francis and Vavrus 2012). While studies suggest that enhanced Arctic warming
397 favors more frequent blocking configurations through a weakened meridional temperature
398 gradient (Cohen et al. 2020), other dynamic factors, including the strengthening of the
399 wintertime North Atlantic jet in recent decades (Woollings et al. 2018) or changes in the
400 stratospheric polar vortex (Kretschmer et al. 2018), might drive the suppression of the ABL
401 pattern identified herein.

402

403 **4.3 Methodological robustness and limitations**

404 While traditional regime classifications typically rely on EOF analysis combined with k-means
405 clustering, our approach leverages the topology-preserving properties of SOM neural networks,
406 followed by hierarchical Ward's clustering. The main advantage of this approach is that SOMs
407 do not force orthogonality onto the extracted patterns, thus enabling a more natural

408 representation of the asymmetric continuum of atmospheric circulation. Furthermore, by
409 assembling 300 SOMs, we significantly mitigate the risk of convergence to local minima, a
410 well-documented limitation of traditional single-initialization k-means clustering approaches
411 (Jain 2010). This ensemble consensus approach ensures that the topological properties of the
412 atmospheric continuum are preserved (Vesanto and Alhoniemi 2000), thereby yielding highly
413 robust and reproducible cluster boundaries (Monti et al. 2003).

414 However, certain limitations must be acknowledged. First, classifying the atmospheric
415 continuum into exactly four EMoCs intrinsically simplifies the vast phase space of circulation
416 variability, more so than detailed region-scale circulation classifications do. While the results
417 of silhouette analysis support this choice, significant intracluster variability remains. Second,
418 our classification is inherently sensitive to the chosen spatial domain. By selecting a European
419 landmass-centric domain (40° W–60° E), we intentionally deprioritized Western Atlantic
420 dynamics in favor of maximizing the explained variance in meteorological variables on the
421 European continent. Future studies should aim to explore in detail how shifting these boundaries
422 modifies the transition probabilities between EMoCs, as this would be particularly useful for
423 ensuring the use of the EMoC approach in seasonal forecasting.

424

425 **4.4 Implications for forecasting and climate projections**

426 In terms of possible future applications of the EMoC classification, its potential in weather
427 forecasting should be explored, as the use of large-scale circulation patterns in extended-range
428 or season-to-season weather forecasts in Europe has been recently highlighted by the European
429 Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (Grams et al. 2020), and such a
430 concept has already been adopted for North America (Lee and Messori 2024). Because the
431 EMoCs were defined directly from Z500A and assigned on daily basis via BMU matching, they
432 can be computed in real time from ensemble forecasts and applied to derive the probabilistic
433 EMoC occurrence and EMoC-conditioned hydroclimate risk (e.g., the likelihood of drought
434 onset under sustained NZT conditions).

435 Another possible application of the EMoC classification could be in projecting the
436 future climate and the occurrence of hydrometeorological extremes. For example, Vautard et
437 al. (2023) reported that Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) simulations
438 generally cannot capture extreme heat events over Western Europe, primarily because of
439 underestimated dynamical contributions, which increases the uncertainty in future projections
440 of heatwaves. The study of changes in large-scale circulation patterns within climate model
441 projections is a viable alternative, particularly for analyzing the probability of extreme events.
442 Rousi et al. (2021) reported that increasing CO₂ concentrations could lead to significant changes
443 in atmospheric circulation patterns over the North Atlantic and Europe, including an increase
444 in the frequency of zonal circulation regimes in DJF and an increase in the occurrence of high-
445 pressure systems in Northwestern Europe in JJA, eventually leading to increased drought risks
446 in Western and Central Europe. Because the EMoC classification requires only Z500A and is
447 not dependent on a very high spatial resolution, applying it to the model outputs of CMIP6 or
448 the upcoming CMIP7 is at hand.

449

450 **5 Conclusion**

451 The main results of the analysis can be summarized as follows:

452 (i) By applying two-stage clustering with an SOM neural network and Ward’s method to 500-
453 hPa geopotential height anomalies within a Europe-centric domain, a new classification of four
454 types of European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) has been developed: Atlantic
455 blocking (ABL), Continental blocking (CBL), Southern zonal track (SZT) and Northern zonal
456 track (NZT).

457 (ii) Each mode exhibits unique characteristic patterns for geopotential height, temperature and
458 precipitation anomalies, as well as for soil-moisture and SST patterns over the European
459 continent and its vicinity. These patterns exhibit seasonal shifts, particularly in the case of
460 temperature and soil moisture, but they remain very stable overall and are distinct from each
461 other.

462 (iii) The existence of consistent spatial patterns of precipitation and soil moisture change across
463 the entire European continent is a significant advantage of this classification, facilitating its
464 potential application in drought forecasting. NZT is exceptionally dry throughout large parts of
465 Europe (particularly in Western and Central Europe), which makes it a suitable indicator of the
466 probable onset of drought in this region.

467 (iv) The EMoC classification offers broader use for the study of recent and future effects of
468 climate change on the occurrence of hydrometeorological extremes in Europe as well as its
469 application in extended-range (season-to-season) forecasts of soil moisture changes and
470 drought risk.

471

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702 **Statements & Declarations**

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716

717 **Conflict of interest**

718 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

719

720 **Consent for publication**

721 All the authors agree on the submission and publication of this paper.

722

723 **Data availability**

724 The data used in this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

725

726 **Supplementary Information**

727 File “Rehor_et_al_Supplementary_Information.pdf” contains following Supplementary
728 Figures:

- 729 (i) **Fig. S1** Silhouette analyses of inter/intra cluster similarity for Wards clusters on 2–
730 30 clustering levels, delimited for combined SOM models based on different
731 numbers of original trained SOM neural networks
- 732 (ii) **Fig. S2** Mean annual anomalies in 200 hPa geopotential heights (a) and 850 hPa
733 geopotential heights (b) for four basic European modes of circulation variability
734 (EMoCs) in 1981–2023 period
- 735 (iii) **Fig. S3** Mean temperature anomalies in four basic European modes of circulation
736 variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-year (WHY)
737 in the 1981–2023 period
- 738 (iv) **Fig. S4** Mean precipitation anomalies during the European modes of circulation
739 variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-year (WHY)
740 in the 1981–2023 period
- 741 (v) **Fig. S5** Mean daily soil moisture change for four basic modes of European
742 circulation variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-
743 year (WHY) in the 1981–2023 period
- 744 (vi) **Fig. S6** Seasonal absolute and relative frequencies of the four basic European modes
745 of circulation variability (EMoCs) in the 1940–2023 period, with 10-year Gaussian
746 smoothing (dashed)

- 747 (vii) **Fig. S7** Mean temperature anomalies during individual European modes of
748 circulation variability (EMoCs) in (a) 1940–1957, (b) 1958–1980 and (c) 1981–
749 2023 periods
- 750 (viii) **Fig. S8** Mean precipitation anomalies during four basic European modes of
751 circulation variability (EMoCs) in (a) 1940–1957, (b) 1958–1980 and (c) 1981–
752 2023 period